

Development of high quality Lignin Based Carbon Fibres

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Green
Chemistry
Recycling
Solution

Introduction

<https://gulfnews.com/opinion/op-eds/worlds-climate-emergency-is-getting-harder-to-ignore-1.65546665>

Sustainable materials

<https://www.vox.com/2014/10/22/18093054/global-warming-explained>

Introduction: Lignin

Becker, *Biotech Adv*, 2019

Patents citing Otani's (1964)

Yuan, *Biotechnol Biofuels* **14**, 205 (2021)

Lignin: Extraction And Challenges For Conversion Into Carbon Material

Successful development of lignin blends for CF precursors

Precursor Fiber

Carbonisation

Carbon fiber

Lignin/blends

Castor oil

Successful development of lignin blends for CF precursors

Direct PF Weave + carbonisation for VARI

Short PF fibres+ carbonisation for sCF + PA injection moulding

Composite car parts

PAN Process

33.34 kgCO₂,eq

Lignin Process

18.12 kgCO₂,eq

- CF Production
- PolyAmide Production
- Injection Moulding Process

Lignin: Extraction And Challenges For Conversion Into Carbon Material

Next Challenge = To produce continuous CF

Problem 1 :

The PF produced have a 80 μm diameter, leading to large CF.

Problem 2 :

Stabilisation step is not efficient enough : Poor crosslinking of the lignin chains leads to fibres breaking at the stabilisation steps.

Solution?

Reactive coatings are used to improve the crosslinking of the lignin chains and reduce their fusibility. The coated fibres are stretched in the stabilisation process

Next Challenge = To produce continuous CF

Reactive coating

UV Treatment	Reactive coating in water bath	% Failure
-	0%	100%
-	1%	50 %
-	2%	17%
-	5%	No Failure
-	10%	No Failure
+	0%	No Failure
+	1%	No Failure
+	2%	No Failure
+	5%	No Failure
+	10%	No Failure

Concentration of RC (%)

Concentration of RC (%)

Next Challenge = To produce continuous CF

Reactive coating

Next Challenge = To produce continuous CF

Improved crosslinking, Less fusing between the fibres and improved carbon yield

0% RC

5% RC

10% RC

Next Challenge = To produce continuous CF

Void less fibres

Concentration of RC (%) 12

Next Challenge = To produce continuous CF

Mechanical properties

Lignin: Extraction And Challenges For Conversion Into Carbon Material

What is next ?

Picture 1. Side view of the complet melt spinning line

Picture 3. Sketch of the carbonisation line

Picture 2. Sketch of the stabilisation (oxidation) line

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Questions?

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What is next ?

Picture 1. Side view of the complet melt spinning line

Picture 3. Sketch of the carbonisation line

Picture 2. Sketch of the stabilisation (oxidation) line

Thank you

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